

Supporting Information for

Fugitive gas migration in the vadose zone at an experimental field site in the Montney shale gas region

Olenka N. Forde^{1,2}, Aaron G. Cahill^{1,3}, Bernhard Mayer⁴, Roger D. Beckie¹ and K. Ulrich

Mayer¹

1. Department of Earth, Ocean and Atmospheric Sciences, University of British Columbia, 2020-2007 Main Mall, Vancouver, BC, V6T 1Z4, Canada

2. now at: Morwick G360 Institute for Groundwater Research, College of Engineering and Physical Science, University of Guelph, 50 Stone Road East, Guelph, ON N1G 2W1, Canada

3. Heriot-Watt University, Lyell Centre, Research Avenue South, Edinburgh, EH14 4AP, United Kingdom

4. Department of Geoscience, University of Calgary, 2500 University Drive NW, Calgary, AB T2N 1N4, Canada

*Corresponding author email: forden@uoguelph.ca phone: (+1) 604 849 1089

Contents of this file

Text: S1

Tables: S1 to S3

Figures: S1 to S9

Introduction

This supporting information includes details on the materials and methods for the simulated natural gas injection, soil gas sampling, soil gas efflux monitoring, and calculations for gas released through a conduit. In addition, we provide tables for calculations, soil gas data, and monitoring infrastructure and, figures for field site location and monitoring network, soil gas effluxes, grain size analysis, soil gas concentrations, soil gas stable carbon isotope ratios, and a conceptual model.

Text S1 Materials and Methods

Simulated natural gas injection

The gas injection rate ($7 \text{ m}^3 \text{ d}^{-1}$) was set assuming that surface casing vent flow rates reported in Alberta and British Columbia, Canada (Nowamooz et al., 2015) are similar to wellbore-leakage rates. An in-line electronic mass-flow controller (Red-y smart GSC-C9SA-BB26) was connected to a gas canister with polyethylene tubing ($\frac{1}{4}$ " ID) to inject the gas through a vertical injection well ($\frac{1}{2}$ " ID polyethylene tubing) in a controlled fashion. The gas injection rate was regulated with the mass flow controller software (Get Red-y, Vögtlin Instruments).

Soil gas molecular and stable carbon isotope measurements

Soil-gas multilevel wells with $\frac{1}{2}$ " ID polyvinyl centre stock tubing were installed at nine locations across the site (Figure S1, Table S1). Each sampling port was accessed through a $\frac{1}{4}$ " ID gas impermeable polyethylene tubing with a mesh screen attached to the bottom and a gas-tight fitting at the top. Soil-gas samples were collected with a gas-tight syringe (Valco Instruments Co.) and a peristaltic pump (0.5 L min^{-1}). Samples were stored in pre-evacuated 12 mL vials (Labco Ltd.) and analyzed for gas composition (CH_4 , CO_2 , N_2 , O_2 , and Ar) and stable-carbon isotope ratios ($^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$) of CH_4 and CO_2 in the Isotope Science Laboratory at the University of Calgary (Alberta, Canada). Analyses for stable-carbon isotopes were completed on a ThermoFisher MAT 253 isotope-ratio mass spectrometer coupled to Trace GC Ultra + GC Isolink (ThermoFisher) (Humez et al., 2016). Isotopic results are reported in the internationally accepted delta ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) notation (in ‰) relative to Vienna PeeDee Belemnite (VPDB) with a precision better than ± 0.5 and ± 0.3 ‰ for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of CH_4 and CO_2 , respectively.

Soil gas efflux monitoring

Seven long-term chambers were connected to a multiplexer (LI-COR LI-8150, LI-COR Inc.) and operated with a CO₂ infra-red gas analyzer (IRGA) (LI-8100, LI-COR Inc.). Water vapor and CO₂ effluxes were continuously measured on the IRGA. Methane effluxes were measured using an extended range (0.01 to 100,000 ppm) Ultraportable Greenhouse Gas Analyzer (UGGA, Los Gatos Research Inc.), which was integrated into the sampling loop (Sihota et al., 2013). Each chamber measurement lasted for 2.5 minutes and was completed approximately every 25 minutes (rotating between all seven chambers). A survey chamber (SC) (LI-8100-103, LI-COR Inc.) connected to an IRGA and an extended-range Greenhouse Gas Analyzer (Los Gatos Research Inc.) was used to measure effluxes across the site between 4-6 hours at up to 123 locations over approximately 70 m² and up to 15 m from the injection location (Figure S1). One round of SC measurements was completed over one day, with a total of 13 measurement rounds conducted over the duration of the experiment. Both survey and long-term chambers were placed on polyvinyl chloride collars (20 cm i.d. covering a 317.8 cm² area) to provide a seal between the chamber and soil. To allow natural conditions to stabilize prior to injection, collars were inserted 4 cm into the soil three weeks before commencing the injection. The exponential increase in soil gas concentrations over 45 sec to 80 sec was used to calculate an efflux (F in $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). The minimum detectable flux (MDF) for CH₄ = 0.01 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ given a $\Delta c = 0.2$ ppm. All analyzers were powered by a 2000-Watt generator and a solar panel system installed by Empower Energy Corp (Kelowna, British Columbia, Canada).

Calculations for gas released through a conduit

For decreasing (Day 1 to 3) and increasing (Day 3 to 5) barometric pressure intervals, we estimated the volume and velocity at which gas transport could be enhanced or restrained, respectively, through a preferential pathway. We assumed that site specific conditions can be represented by a reservoir with gas stored at the injection depth (12 m bgs), and that a conduit (preferential pathway) through the soil allowed barometric pressure changes to penetrate into the vadose zone. Using this approach, the volume and velocity of gas movement from the reservoir through the conduit was calculated by:

- 1) Total volume of reservoir gas due to pressure change:

$$[V_{tot_f}] = [p_i] * [V_{tot_i}] / [p_f]$$

$$[del_V] = [V_{tot_f}] - [V_{tot_i}]$$

- 2) Volume of gas released through the conduit:

$$[del_V] = [V_{tot_f}] - [V_{tot_i}]$$

- 3) Number of pore volumes of conduit displaced:

$$[N_p] = [del_V] / [V_c]$$

- 4) Number of pore volumes displaced over duration of pressure change:

$$[N_{p_d}] = [N_p] / [del_t]$$

- 5) Average gas flow velocity in conduit over duration of pressure change:

$$[v_{gas}] = [N_{p_d}] / [L_c]$$

For both increasing and decreasing barometric pressure scenarios, it was assumed that the volume reservoir was 50 m³ and the volume of the conduit was between 0.01 m³ and 1 m³ (results in Table S3 are for 0.01 m³). The larger the conduit volume, the less pore volumes displaced over a pressure change and at a slower the gas flow velocity.

Tables

Table S1. Locations of the long-term chambers (LT-Ch) and multilevel wells (MW) with distance from injection.

Monitoring device	X distance from injection (m)	Y distance from injection (m)
LT-Ch1	0	0
LT-Ch2	1	0
LT-Ch3	2	0
LT-Ch4	5	0
LT-Ch5	0	1
LT-Ch6	0	2
LT-Ch7	0	5
MW2	1	0
MW3	2	0
MW4	5	0
MW5	10	0
MW6	0	1
MW7	0	2
MW8	0	5
MW9	0	10

Table S2. Range in baseline soil gas concentrations % (v/v) across all nine multilevel wells at the respective depths bgs and measured three days before gas injection. Concentrations below detection limit are shown as non-detect (ND).

Depth (m)	O ₂	N ₂	Ar	CO ₂	CH ₄
1	16.9-20.7	78.0-80.8	0.93-0.98	0.07-1.1	ND-0.0004
2	16.8-19.8	77.8-81.2	0.93-1.0	0.99-1.7	ND-0.0003
3	16.3-19.4	77.8-81.3	0.95-1.0	1.2-2.4	ND-0.0003
4	16.0-18.6	78.3-81.0	0.94-0.98	1.5-2.6	ND-0.0003
5	15.7-17.5	79.4-80.8	0.93-0.99	1.9-2.8	ND-0.0003
6	16.1-17.6	78.7-80.7	0.93-0.98	2.1-3.0	ND-0.0002
7	16.5-17.5	78.8-80.0	0.93-0.98	2.3-3.4	ND-0.0004
8	16.7-17.5	78.9-79.7	0.93-0.98	2.4-3.1	ND-0.0007
9	16.9-17.5	78.8-80.1	0.94-1.0	2.4-3.1	0.0002-0.0003
10	17.1-17.7	78.8-79.4	0.98-0.98	2.3-3.1	0.0001-0.0004
11	16.9-17.4	78.7-79.4	0.93-1.0	2.7-3.1	ND-0.0002
12	16.6-16.8	78.7-79.2	0.93-1.0	3.2-3.4	ND-0.0002

Table S3. Parameter used to estimate the volume and velocity of gas transport through a conduit during decreasing and increasing barometric pressure intervals.

Parameter	Unit	Value		
		Day 1 to 3 (BP. Decreasing)	Day 3 to 5 (BP. Increasing)	
Volume reservoir	V _r	[L]	50000	50000
Volume conduit	V _c	[L]	0.01	0.01
Total volume	V _{tot}	[L]	50010	50010
Initial pressure	p _i	[atm]	0.93	0.9099
Final pressure	p _f	[atm]	0.91	0.9326
Pressure change	del _p	[mbar]	0.016	-0.0227
Duration pressure change	del _t	[d]	3	3
Length conduit	L _c	[m]	12	12
Total volume from pressure change	V _{tot_f}	[L]	50878	48793
Volume gas released	del _V	[L]	868	-1217
Pore volumes of conduit displaced	N _p	[-]	29	-122
Pore volumes displaced over duration of pressure change	N _{p_d}	[d ⁻¹]	12	-20
Average gas flow velocity in conduit over duration of pressure change	v _{gas}	[m d ⁻¹]	347	-487
Response to pressure change	t	[hr]	0.83	0.59

Figures

Figure S1. A) Site location in Hudson's Hope, British Columbia, Canada. B) Monitoring network including seven long-term chambers (LT-Ch), natural gas injection well (IW), and eight multilevel wells (MW) for soil gas sampling. The location of each monitoring device is given in Table S1. C) Core log collected from a sonic drill hole near the injection location, outside the monitoring grid. The injection well was 12 m bgs, as indicated by the red line.

Figure S2. Methane effluxes from LT-Chs 1, 2, 3, 4, and 7 (upper figure) and LT-Chs 5 and 6 (lower figure) with barometric pressure over the duration of the experiment. Effluxes were highest at LT-Ch6, but all LT-Chs showed the same temporal trend with a direct response to changes in barometric pressure.

Figure S3. Methane effluxes measured across the site using the SC on select days. Higher CH_4 effluxes with a larger surface flux area were measured on days during a decreasing barometric pressure cycle (Day 3, 4, and 21).

Figure S4. Grain size analysis from the gas injection location (modified from Forde et al., 2019). Low permeability silts and clays are dominant between 10 m to 2.80 m, with more fine sand 12 m bgs.

Figure S5. Soil gas concentrations of Ar, CH₄, N₂, and O₂ over time from 2 m, 6m, 11 m, and 12 m bgs at MW2, MW7 and MW8. Lower panel shows barometric pressure and CH₄ effluxes over time from long-term chambers LT-Ch2, LT-Ch6, and LT-Ch7 co-located with MWs.

Figure S6. Carbon dioxide effluxes from LT-Chs 1, 2, 3, 4, and 7 (upper figure) and LT-Chs 5 and 6 (lower figure) with barometric pressure over the duration of the experiment. Effluxes for CO₂ were highest at LT-Ch6 and responded directly to changes in barometric pressure. At all other LT-Chs, CO₂ effluxes decreased over time.

Figure S7. Stable carbon isotope ratios for CO_2 and CH_4 collected from all MWs during (Day 0 - 5) and post injection (Day 5 - 35), and on Day 400. Injected gas had $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ values of -45‰ and -11‰, respectively. Trends of $\delta^{13}\text{C-CH}_4$ towards values > -45 ‰ coupled with decreasing $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ demonstrates progressive CH_4 oxidation. $\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ values predominantly reflect signatures from degradation of soil organic matter ($\delta^{13}\text{C-CO}_2$ -23‰ to -21‰).

Figure S8. Soil gas concentrations for O₂, CO₂ and N₂ plotted versus CH₄ for all MWs at 2 m (green), 6 m (blue), 11 m (grey) and 12 m bgs (red) collected before (diamonds), during (Day 0 to 5, circles) and post injection (Day 5 to 35, triangles), and on Day 400 (squares). The composition of air and injected natural gas are shown with black markers. Dashed mixing lines between baseline gas present in the vadose zone and injected gas bracket mixing for upper and lower baseline conditions. Since O₂ and CO₂ concentrations vary between sampling points and as a function of depth at baseline conditions, it is not possible to identify a single mixing line. However, the effect of mixing can be bracketed based on maximum and minimum O₂ and CO₂ background concentrations (blue region). A departure of gas composition from the average mixing line and the bracketed region of mixing indicates the occurrence of processes in addition to mixing.

Figure S9. Conceptual model of fugitive GM in a deep vadose zone with a network of long-term chambers (LT-Ch) and soil gas monitoring wells (MW). A 3D inverse distancing interpolation of CH₄ soil gas concentrations is shown for intervals of decreasing (Day 3) and increasing (Day 5) barometric-pressure that occurred during the experimental injection simulating natural-gas leakage. The circular markers in the contours represent soil-gas sampling locations at every 1 m interval bgs.